

Review THE PORTRAYAL OF AMERICAN CULTURE AND SUICIDE IN THE SONG “1-800-273-8255” SUNG BY LOGIC (FT. ALESSIA CARA & KHALID)

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Abstract

This paper will analyze a song entitled 1-800-273-8255 sung by Logic, ft. Alessia Cara and Khalid. This analysis will focus on the meaning of the song lyrics that relate to the issue of suicide and also the purpose of the text features and context in the song. This song is a literary work that contains unwanted events. This song tells about the way people in the United States and even the world, face and respond to the problems they have in ways other than suicide (Niederkrotenthaler & Draper, 2021). Therefore, we can discuss other options that the community can use. The reason for choosing this song is because it illustrates the importance of the issue globally and aims to warn the issue.

Keywords: *Meaning, suicide, songs, global issues, purpose.*

A. Introduction

Suicide killed more than 820,000 people globally in 2015, up from 712,000 in 1990. As such, suicide is the tenth leading cause of death globally. Suicide is a way to end someone's life. Suicide is mainly caused by depression, personality disorders, bipolar disorder, anxiety disorders, etc. Some suicides are often caused by stress caused by relationship problems such as bullying or even a breakup, another good example is

financial problems such as bankruptcy and business closures. Those who have attempted suicide in the past have a higher risk of attempting suicide in the future. Several methods, including the misuse of firearms, toxic substances and drugs, are suicide methods used in modern times. So, it can be done by limiting their access to these prohibited items.

Successful suicide rates for men are significantly higher than for women, ranging from 1.5 times higher in developing countries to 3.5 times higher in developed countries. In some countries, suicide is most common in people over the age of 70, while in others, people between the ages of 15 and 35 have the highest suicide risk. In western countries, suicide attempts are more common in women and adolescents. Views about suicide are influenced by various existential themes, such as religion, the importance of life, and honor. In the Abrahamic religion, suicide was often seen as an insult to God. In the 21st century, suicide is widely used as a protest, as suicide bombings are a terrorist tactic and even as a military strategy.

Suicide is a major public health problem in the United States. The United States has one of the highest suicide rates of any wealthy nation. 48,344 suicides were recorded in 2018 (Morgan & Rowhani-Rahbar, 2021), up from 42,773 in 2014. From 1999 to 2014, the annual suicide rate in the United States has increased from 10.5 suicides per 100,000 people to 24% from 130.0 per 100,000 people in the United States. This is also a record high in the last 28 years. Most of the suicide cases go unreported because they are covered up by the victim's family to maintain the privacy of the victim and the family of the victim (American Foundation for Suicide Prevention, 2021). The suicide rate among adolescents in Western countries is relatively high. These youths are dominated by women under the age of 21. If the person attempts suicide but is unsuccessful, it is called a suicide attempt. Between the 1960s and 1980s, adolescent suicide rates nearly tripled, making suicide the third leading cause of death in the United States (Rudd, 1989). There are many factors that influence adolescent suicide, such as academic stress, alcohol consumption, relationship problems, etc. Although harassment is the leading cause of suicide among adolescents, those who are unsure of their gender identity are more likely to attempt suicide, especially those who have experienced harassment and bullying

B. Findings

The result of the analytical technique used in this study is that the song can be understood by placing our minds in the position of the songwriter. Then, the meaning of the song can be obtained from the original lyrics of the song which is then converted into its actual meaning. The song's actual lyrics are the writer's literal way of expressing his/her emotions while the non-literal translation represents how the songwriter's shows his/her logical thinking through this song. The results of this study are the analysis phase using the lyrics of the song "1-800-273-8255" which is sung by Logic. The analysis phase that takes place aims to reveal the true meaning behind the song (Anggraina, 2019). Analysis and elaboration are then given in the discussion to improve the understanding of the song.

Pre-Chorus (Original)

I've been on the low, I been taking my time

I feel like I'm out of my mind

It feel like my life ain't mine

Who can relate?

I've been on the low, I been taking my time

I feel like I'm out of my mind

It feel like my life ain't mine

Actual meaning

This is a debate in a person's mind who is depressed and wants to end his/her life by committing suicide, in which this situation can happen to anyone.

Chorus (Original)

I don't wanna be alive

I don't wanna be alive

I just wanna die today

I just wanna die

I don't wanna be alive

I don't wanna be alive

I just wanna die

And let me tell you why

Actual meaning

This is the first thing a depressed person should say when calling a suicide helpline. The lyrics are a little scary, but the situation is realistic because so many people are suicidal and say it before deciding to end their life. With this song, Logic wants to show the reality of his listeners.

Verse 1 (Original)

All this other shit I'm talkin' 'bout they think they know it

I've been praying for somebody to save me, no one's heroic

And my life don't even matter

I know it, I know it, I know I'm hurting deep down but can't show it

I never had a place to call my own

I never had a home

Ain't nobody callin' my phone

Where you been? Where you at? What's on your mind?

They say every life precious but nobody care about mine

Actual meaning

This was the voice of the person calling the American National Suicide Prevention operator. The man's condition and the mood was very unstable, and in his vent, it was said that no one cared about him.

Chorus (Original)

I want you to be alive

I want you to be alive

You don't gotta die today

You don't gotta die

I want you to be alive

I want you to be alive

You don't gotta die

Now lemme tell you why

Actual meaning

Here's the response from the operator at the American National Suicide Prevention. This may sound short and simple, but his words bring encouragement to depressed and hopeless people in their lives.

Verse 2 (Original)

It's the very first breath

When your head's been drowning underwater

And it's the lightness in the air

When you're there

Chest to chest with a lover

It's holding on, though the road's long

And seeing light in the darkest things

And when you stare at your reflection

Finally knowing who it is

I know that you'll thank God you did

Actual meaning

"Drowning" is a metaphor for despair. However, the operator tells the caller "it's a first breath", which means the caller can get new hope from the despair the caller is experiencing. The operator then explains that at this point, the caller should accept whatever is insulting him and only accept the positive values of all that is happening. Not only that, the operator also said that the caller should accept himself, which is a good step to be more grateful, which makes the caller not alone. So if everyone keep cultivating positive thoughts, everyone will be able to survive.

Verse 3 (Original)

I know where you been, where you are, where you goin'

I know you're the reason I believe in life

What's the day without a little night?

I'm just tryna shed a little light

It can be hard

It can be so hard

But you gotta live right now

You got everything to give right now

Actual meaning

In this section, the operator tells the caller that he is not the only one who has experienced this situation, many others have experienced a similar situation and are still surviving to this day. The operator then makes sure the caller gets through everything.

Closing Chorus (Original)

I finally wanna be alive (finally wanna be alive)

I finally wanna be alive

I don't wanna die today (hey)

I don't wanna die

I finally wanna be alive (finally wanna be alive)

I finally wanna be alive (oh)

I don't wanna die (no, I don't wanna die)

I don't wanna die

(I just wanna live)

(I just wanna live)

Pain don't hurt the same, I know

The lane I travel feels alone

But I'm moving 'til my legs give out

And I see my tears melt in the snow

But I don't wanna cry

I don't wanna cry anymore

I wanna feel alive

I don't even wanna die anymore

Oh I don't wanna

I don't wanna

I don't even wanna die anymore

Actual meaning

After a caller talks to an operator at an American National Suicide Prevention, the man finally regains his will to live. Sometimes, such catharsis can make one feel calm and finally be able to see the dawn of the world again.

C. Discussion

The first verse of the song is presented from the point of view of a caller who wants to commit suicide because of the kind of tragedy that makes the person want to take his own life.

This may sound irritating and cannot be sugar-coated. Of course, many people think about this every day, but not everyone does it. For example, what would happen if we slapped a random person in the face? We already know the consequences, and these people may not be prepared for the consequences. So, these people had to take inspiration from this song to let them know what was real.

Logic knew this was a very frightening event that would haunt anyone who had to go through it. That's why Logic makes songs that make listeners feel connected and everything will be fine. Not everyone can show this to someone who is going through a certain stage in their life, but Logic will show it and he will show it through this song. The first verse shows how a man felt so hopeless and felt that at the lowest point of his life there was no hope of being saved again. This verse also shows that no one cares about what they're going through or that their parents care or love them enough, which is why the song's title is 1800, so people quickly turn to someone for help via this hotline.

The hook and the second verse of the song are performed from the perspective of operators from the National Suicide Prevention Lifeline (NSPL), who offers to help and tell them why they are moving on with their lives.

There's a feeling of pressure in people's chests when something is making them feel down and makes them feel like the air is hard to breathe, but it is irrelevant when they feel loved and someone cares about them. In the second verse of the song adds a lighthearted feeling of relief, as the light illuminates someone with the people who come into their life, teaching them to see things from a new perspective. Not only that, the music video for the song shows the experiences of gay teens, including the coming out. So, no matter what happens, don't give up on life.

The third verse is the part where Logic interacts with his audience and tells them that everything is going to be okay, that things will get better, and instead of complaining, Logic wants his audience to recognize the positives in their life and appreciate them.

In the closing chorus, Logic shows that previously suicidal depressed patients have now calmed down, have seen the new life landscape in front of them, are not committing suicide, and just want to live. Here too, the caller learns his lesson and becomes a stronger, more independent, more active person, given a second chance at life and taking advantage of the new opportunities that are coming.

D. Conclusion

The message of the song is very clear. Until now artists, including artists and singers or people who can influence others, have direct sympathy and empathy for those who think their lives are not worth living. At first, logic does this by realistically depicting the person's character as his own, and therefore through this, it is seen that most artists represent their emotions through the art they produce and true meanings can be obtained with logical thinking. This song is dedicated to telling people suffering from depression that taking drastic action against this negativity is not the answer. The experience of depression is not permanent but when one does experience it, one has to try harder to truly acknowledge the gift of love to convince oneself that the pain will never end.

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